

WAYS TO IMPROVE THE SEGMENTATION PROCESS OF FURNITURE PRODUCTS MARKET IN SAMARKAND REGION

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Abstract. This article is devoted to research of the market of furniture production status of Samarkand region. The authors proposed specific signs of segmentation of the furniture market.

Key words: furniture market, furniture assortment, segmentation.

ПУТИ УЛУЧШЕНИЯ ПРОЦЕССА СЕГМЕНТАЦИИ РЫНКА МЕБЕЛЬНОЙ ПРОДУКЦИИ САМАРКАНДСКОЙ ОБЛАСТИ

Аннотация. Данная статья посвящена исследованию состояния рынка мебельной продукции Самаркандской области. Автором предложены специфические признаки сегментирования рынка мебели.

Ключевые слова: рынок мебельной продукции, ассортимент мебели, сегментирование.

INTRODUCTION

In our country, certain industries play an important role in the production of consumer goods, filling the domestic consumer market and the production of import-substituting products. These include the woodworking and furniture industries.

The furniture and woodworking industry of the Republic of Uzbekistan is one of the fastest growing industries in the country. If in previous years 65-70% of the domestic furniture market was filled with products of foreign manufacturers, today more than 90% of demand is met by high-quality furniture products manufactured in our country. Today, there are more than 1,500 enterprises in the field of furniture and woodworking industries in the country. These include such enterprises as the creation of finished furniture products, the production of furniture raw materials, the production of various accessories, the production of semi-finished products, and the primary processing of wood.

Samarkand region is one of the leaders in furniture production in the country. As of January 1, 2020, there are 117 organizations specializing in woodworking and furniture production in the region.

Furniture factories are those that specialize in one product or that specialize in several types of products. Of these, 91 organizations (77.8%) specialize in one product, 15 organizations (12.8%) - in two or three product ranges, and 11 organizations (9.4%) produce four or more products. In 2020, these organizations produced 128672.1 million soums, which is 13.7% more than in 2019. Created product Finished furniture in the amount of 112376.9 million soums, 16295.2 million soums - separate components for furniture. [1]

METHOD AND METHODOLOGY

At the same time, the analysis shows that the latter group of organizations produces 19.87% of finished furniture products. This means that diversified furniture enterprises are more efficient than other specialized enterprises.

The existence of several approaches to product classification in the furniture industry creates problems in the conduct of market activities. For example, in statistical reporting, furniture products are divided into the following groups:

- Mainly furniture for seating on a metal frame;
- Seating furniture not elsewhere classified;
- Wooden furniture for institutions;
- Kitchen furniture;
- Beds (except bed bases);
- Wooden bedroom furniture (except for hanging wardrobes, bed bases, lamps and chandeliers, floor mirrors, seating furniture);
- Wooden furniture for living rooms and living rooms (except floor mirrors, seating furniture).

Furniture components are also divided into separate groups according to production technologies, materials used and functions:

- Seating furniture;
- Furniture items (except for seating furniture);
- Metal furniture for institutions;
- Services to subcontractors for the implementation of a part (or separate operations) of the process of manufacturing furniture for furniture and their parts, parts of other furniture.

Table 1.

Assortment of furniture products manufactured in the Samarkand region in 2020 *

T / p	Furniture type	Number of enterprises	Productive capacity,		Sum	
				%	million sum	%
A. Finished furniture						
1	Seating furniture mainly on a metal frame, pcs.	15	288636	45.37	9755.2	8.68
2	Seating furniture, not included in other groups, pcs.	31 year	97938	15.39	46796.2	41.64
3	Wooden furniture for institutions, pcs.	25	36049	5.67	12422.6	11.05
4	Furniture for kitchen	26 year	191141	30.04	6145.2	5.47
5	Beds (without frame), pcs.	7	6263	0.98	2475.2	2.2
6	Wooden furniture for the bedroom, pcs.	23	6010	0.94	13456.6	11.97
7	Wooden furniture for living rooms and living rooms, pcs.	eighteen	10168	1.60	21325.8	18.98
	Jami	145	636205	100	112376.9	100
B. Individual components for furniture						
1	Seating furniture, tn	2	7.17		192.8	1.18
2	Furniture items (except for seating furniture), ton	12	707.0		2197.4	13.48

3	Metal furniture for institutions, tn	5	3553.3		7742.1	47.51
4	Seat furniture and its parts, services of a subcontractor for the implementation of a part of the production process of other furniture parts, mln. Rub. sum	7	6162.8		6162.8	37.82
		26 year	-	-	16295.2	100
			-		128672.1	

* - The table was compiled according to the data of the Statistics Department of the Samarkand region.

RESEARCH RESULTS

The first conclusion from the table is that all enterprises of the region are engaged in the production of finished furniture products, and components are produced at 26 enterprises. If we consider finished furniture products in natural sizes, then only Most of 636 205 products furniture for residential premises with a metal frame (288,636 pieces, or 45.37%) and kitchen furniture (191,141 pieces or 30.04%). The rest of the furniture does not play a significant role in natural dimensions. The analysis of the composition of components is fraught with a number of difficulties, since their units of measurement cannot be compared with the amount of products.

The data in monetary terms show that among the finished furniture products, the production of upholstered furniture, which is not included in another group, occupies a large place (41.64%), followed by wooden furniture for dining rooms and living rooms (18.98%). Least of all is the production of mattresses (2.2%).

In the section of individual manufacturers, various assortment brands of furniture products are used. For example, in LLC "Gulobod Mebel" the classification of furniture is as follows: kitchen furniture, upholstered furniture, office furniture, bedroom furniture, wooden tables and chairs, coffee tables, mattresses. It can be seen that the classification of products used in enterprises is completely different.

In the marketing program, taking into account the location of the product range, it is important to choose the main directions of its management. One of the main directions of increasing competitiveness is expanding the range of activities of furniture manufacturers. In our opinion, when creating a marketing program, the main emphasis should be placed on the following areas of product expansion:

- Focusing buyers' attention on furniture sets, that is, the formation of an assortment in accordance with the principles of complementarity. It is necessary to create product catalogs based on the needs of customers, to explain in detail the production flow charts, to offer scientifically grounded furniture for premises for various purposes. As an example, we offer furniture for hotels. In accordance with the instructions of the President, in the coming years it is planned to increase the number of foreign tourists to 12 million. [2] For this, the number of hotels in our country should be almost tripled, and all of them will be equipped with furniture according to world standards.

- Expansion and development of signs of segmentation of the furniture market. Research has shown that the above classification of furniture does not fully reflect its level of suitability for customers. This classification is not focused on customer segmentation based on socio-psychological, demographic and behavioral characteristics.

To improve segmentation efficiency and offer clear perspectives for furniture businesses, we propose the following approach (Table 2). In the table, we present some proposals for the formation of the assortment for the enterprises of the furniture industry, but they can be supplemented and developed by each enterprise.

Table 2.

Classification of the furniture market by demographic and socio-psychological characteristics and the formation of a product range.

General classification mark	More classification mark	Market segment	Offer for a range of products
By the purpose of buildings	Accommodation	Apartment in a multi-storey building, (standard)	Furniture of the exact size, standard shape, mutually compatible set
		Apartment in a multi-storey building (free space)	Dimensionless furniture designed according to a separate design
		Model houses (finished project)	Assortment of designed type (catalog)
		Individual houses (unregulated)	Free custom-made furniture, custom-made
	Non-residential premises	Social facilities (finished project)	Large batches, sanitary approved kits of approved shape
		Offices (individual project)	In a specific structure, but custom-made
		Public buildings (free space)	Furniture of various shapes based on a free project on site.
		Hotel, restaurant	A set of standard and individual furniture of a luxury and modern level.

		Premises for sales and service	The furniture is mainly manufactured from standard components assembled on site.
Demographic and socio-psychological characteristics	Buyer's age and family life cycle	Brides and grooms	Luxury furniture, mainly bedroom furniture.
		Young family (for the purpose of living separately)	Standard furniture, all kinds of household items.
		Stable family	Compatible furniture set, modern design, separate order
		Single-parent family	Standard level separate furniture
	Income	Low income	Standard level
		Average income	State-of-the-art in the catalog
		High income	Luxury level, custom design
	Role and lifestyle in society	Market leader, fashion fan	We offer a unique design and material
		Convenience maker	
		Modern	
Adapted to the same conditions (conservatively)			
Location	Located in the village		
	Located in the city		

CONCLUSION

On the basis of our proposals, it is necessary to form consumer demand - to take into account a wider range of conditions and pay attention not only to its width, but also to its depth when forming the assortment. We are confident that the application of these proposals in every furniture company will contribute to increasing the competitiveness in the market.

REFERENCES

1. Sh.M. Mirziyoev "New Development Strategy of Uzbekistan" completed second edition, Tashkent "Uzbekistan" publishing house, 2022, 416 p.
2. Sh.M. Mirziyoev "Humanity, goodness and creativity are the foundations of our national idea" Tashkent "TASVIR" publishing house, 2021 y 36 p.
3. The first President of the Republic of Uzbekistan I.A. Karimov "Our main task is to further increase the development of our country and the prosperity of our people" Tashkent: Uzbekistan, 2010. 18 p.

4. Abduganiev A., Tolametova Z. Labor capacity of Uzbekistan. T.: "Labor", 1998. 96 p.
5. Under the editorship of K.K. Abdurakhmonov. - T.: Human development. Textbook. i.f.d., prof. "Science and technology", 2013.
6. Derevyagina L.N., Ivashkova N.I. Obit training marketing specialists in the system of additional professional education // Vestnik. 2001
7. Nasirov P. Abdullayeva L. Marketing is the basis of market economy. T.: "Teacher" 2008.
8. Bekmurodov A.Sh., Kosimova M.S., Safarov B.J., Marketing management: Study guide. - T.: TDIU, 2007. - 268 p.
9. Begmatov Sh. A. Kakhorov A.J. Scientific and methodological problems of introducing innovative marketing, "Economics and Education" magazine No. 5, September-October, 2016.
10. Musaeva Sh.A. Usmonova D.I. Innovative marketing: Study guide. - "TURON PUBLISHING" Samarkand 2021.
11. Azimovna M. S., Shokhrukhovich U. F., Sodirovich U. B. Problems in the Implementation of Quality Management Systems in Small Business Enterprises //Eurasian Research Bulletin. – 2022. – T. 7. – C. 54-57.
12. Azimovna M. S., Ilkhomovna U. D. Problems of Marketing in the System of Higher Education //Academic Journal of Digital Economics and Stability. – 2022. – T. 13. – C. 71-75.
13. Azimovna M. S., Ilkhomovna U. D., Shokhrukhovich U. F. INNOVATIVE STRATEGIES OF TOURISM DEVELOPMENT IN UZBEKISTAN //EUROPEAN JOURNAL OF INNOVATION IN NONFORMAL EDUCATION. – 2022. – T. 2. – №. 1. – C. 1-4.
14. Musayeva S. A., Usmonova D. I., Usmanov F. S. Problems with Marketing Research in the Furniture Market //Eurasian Journal of Academic Research. – 2021.
15. Azimovna M. S., Shokhrukhovich U. F. Development Prospects of Business Subjects in the Republic of Uzbekistan //Web of Scholars: Multidimensional Research Journal. – 2022. – T. 1. – №. 4. – C. 13-19.
16. Azimovna M. S., Ilkhomovna U. D., Shokhrukhovich U. F. The Concept of Marketing Policy in Trade and Service Enterprises //CENTRAL ASIAN JOURNAL OF INNOVATIONS ON TOURISM MANAGEMENT AND FINANCE. – 2022. – T. 3. – №. 8. – C. 1-5.
17. SCIENCE AND INNOVATION INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC JOURNAL VOLUME 1 ISSUE 5 UIF-2022: 8.2 | ISSN: 2181-3337
18. 105
19. Azimovna M. S., Shokhrukhovich U. F. Ways to expand network marketing and e-commerce in the wholesale of medicines //INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF RESEARCH IN COMMERCE, IT, ENGINEERING AND SOCIAL SCIENCES ISSN: 2349-7793 Impact Factor: 6.876. – 2022. – T. 16. – №. 06. – C. 113-116.
20. Azimovna M. S., Abdurozикович M. Z. Features of the pharmaceutical market of the Republic of Uzbekistan //INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF SOCIAL SCIENCE & INTERDISCIPLINARY RESEARCH ISSN: 2277-3630 Impact factor: 7.429. – 2022. – T. 11. – №. 06. – C. 201-206.
21. Azimovna M. S., Shokhrukhovich U. S. THE ROLE OF AGRICULTURAL PRODUCTS IN THE FOREIGN TRADE TURNOVER OF THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN

- //BARQARORLIK VA YETAKCHI TADQIQOTLAR ONLAYN ILMIY JURNALI. – 2022. – T. 2. – №. 6. – C. 110-112.
22. Azimovna M. S. IMPROVING THE STUDY OF CONSUMER BEHAVIOR //Gospodarka i Innowacje. – 2022. – C. 109-112.
23. Azimovna M. S. et al. Analysis of the main economic and marketing indicators of FE" DAKA-TEX" LLC //ASIA PACIFIC JOURNAL OF MARKETING & MANAGEMENT REVIEW ISSN: 2319-2836 Impact Factor: 7.603. – 2022. – T. 11. – №. 06. – C. 4-7.
24. Azimovna M. S., Ilkhomovna U. D. Optimal principles of assessing the quality of graduates in higher education //Eurasian Scientific Herald. – 2022. – T. 8. – C. 233-238.
25. Azimovna M. S. THE MAIN DIRECTIONS OF THE MARKETING COMPLEX TO INCREASE THE EXPORT POTENTIAL OF PRODUCTS //FORMATION OF PSYCHOLOGY AND PEDAGOGY AS INTERDISCIPLINARY SCIENCES. – 2022. – T. 1. – №. 9. – C. 20-23.
26. 24.MS Azimovna Improving The Study Of Consumer Behavior
27. Gospodarka i Innowacje., 109-112
28. 25.MS Azimovna Stages of the Econometric Research and Modeling Process
29. Central Asian Journal of Innovations on Tourism Management and Finance 3 (10 ...
30. 26.MS Azimovna Scientific-Methodical Issues of Evaluation of Marketing Service in Hotels
31. Central Asian Journal of Innovations on Tourism Management and Finance 3 (10
32. 27. MS Azimovna Efficiency of advertising activities of trading organizations and ways to increase IT